

Structural Equation Modeling factors affecting the development of sport entrepreneurship in Hamedan province

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was Structural Equation Modeling factors affecting the development of sport entrepreneurship in Hamedan province from the perspective of post-graduate students. The research method was analytical-descriptive and was conducted in a survey method. The study population consisted of all post-graduate students of physical education in the Hamedan province (N=200). Based on Morgan's table, 130 people were selected to this research with random sampling. The survey instrument consisted of a researcher made questionnaire with the Likert scale. Data analysis was performed by descriptive statistics and Friedman ranking test. Also, structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to model design. The results of Friedman ranking test showed that economic, cultural- social, political -legal and environmental factors had the highest rank respectively. The results of path analysis also suggested that economic factors with path coefficient of ($pc = 0.76$), Socio-cultural factors ($pc = 0.61$), political -legal factors ($pc = 0.50$) and ultimately environmental factors ($pc = 0.33$) had the highest effect in development of sport entrepreneurship in Hamadan province.

Keywords: Student, Economic factors, Entrepreneurship, SEM

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